

EXPERIENCES OF JUNIOR HIGH-STUDENT MOTHERS IN MAGUINDANAO I DIVISION

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Experiences of Junior High-Student Mothers in Maguindanao I Division

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Abstract

Evidence suggests that junior high school as well as student mothers are more likely to be affected by social problems associated with poor health and poverty. Student mothers are overwhelming headed by women. Despite their increasing number and their level of vulnerability, the lived experiences of student mothers have attracted little attention in the literature. Still little is known about many aspects of life as experienced by them. This study that explored the lived experienced of junior high student mothers at the junior high school in Maguindanao I Division. This qualitative research draws on a Phenomenological method was utilized in the conduct of the study. It is a qualitative study that used purposive sampling, data was collected through individual interviews and which were transcribed and analysed using a thematic content analysis approach. Findings were grouped into the following themes and subthemes; the positive and negative experiences, simultaneous management, comprehensive support. The study also determined the aspiration and realization of the student mothers .Another findings of this study revealed that the student mothers' major concern were time management and the social support. However, their being in the junior high school life experiences signified happiness because they are able to accept their life as student mothers. The findings of this study imply that there is a need to provide these student mothers with social, moral guidance and technical services to enhance their skills useful for playing dual roles.

Keywords: *experiences, student, mothers, division*

Introduction

The Philippines teenage pregnancy rate has increased by 60% in a year 2000- 2010, according to the Philippine National Statistic Office. This is very alarming. Teenage pregnancy often occurs between the ages of 15-19 years old, often in this age the girls are still studying.

The life of student mother is no easy feat they have to juggle their time between attending their classes, making their requirements, taking care of their child and taking care of the house. They become the primary caregiver of their child and are expected to rear their child well. Many of these student mothers also engage in working part-time to help in the financial burden of both studying and caring for the child. But, this becomes another disadvantage as it takes up time and effort on the part of the student mother.

Education becomes a lesser priority and is often delayed until they are able to leave the children at home are financially stable. But there are girls who are studying as well as taking care of their child and they are who we call student mothers. The burden for these girls have double as to they have to take care of school as well as their child at home.

Student mothers experiences unpleasant emotional pressures and receive negative feedback from academic setting therefore, taking on motherhood along with studies is not considered a normal in junior high school. Many student mothers have expresses feeling of guilt, worry and inadequacy in both as a student and as a mother. But there are girls who are studying as well as taking care of their children and they are known to called student mothers.

Research Questions

This study aimed to understand and determine their experiences towards their studies as well as child rearing. More specifically, what are the positive and negative experiences they have encountered in studying while nurturing their child at home. The study also seeks to find the coping strategy used by student mothers in their situation. With these in mind the purpose of the study is to help the readers understand the endeavours experienced by student mothers. Specifically, it Sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the experiences of a Junior High Student Mother in Maguindanao I ?
2. What are the Aspiration and Realization of Junior High Student
3. Mother ?

Literature Review

From 2000 to 2010, the number of live births by teenage mothers in the Philippines rose by more than 60 percent, latest data from the National statistic office Showed. Another alarming fact is that the number of teenage mothers who gave birth to their second or third child during their teenage year has increase in the last ten years. This according to the data shown in the press conference in Quezon City by Carmelita Ericta, administrator and civil registrar general of the National statistic office.(Ime Morales, July 9,2013).Teenage pregnancy is a global issue and a major contributor to school drop-out among girls. Permanent expulsion was one of the solutions made for teenage pregnancy but this has been proven ineffective and unfair to the girls. Now there is a return to school policy where a student is temporarily dismissed from school due to teenage pregnancy or student mothers. Some previous presentation showed that the

phenomenon of early marriage was related to the high poverty and social constraints due to conflict, political, economical obstacle, instability, shortage service in education, housing, and professional development. Published on 23rd March, 2015 In many different countries and part of the world young women's marriage before the age of 18 is a reality to be lived and showed that a considerable percentage of women in civilized and develop countries continue to marry at an early age. It was common that parents encourage their daughter to get marriage at an early age in hope that this marriage will enhanced both their financial and social status. However, early marriage as well as Junior High Student Mothers is considered as a form of violation of human right, since it compromised the physical, mental, psychological, educational, and emotional development of the girls. In the Philippines education has been recognized to central element in development. The decision and determination to pursue a higher education is the one of the most significant commitment a student will make in her or his life time. The pressure of family survival or of improving a family's socio-economic status combines with parents' own attitude toward education, ultimately determined whether or not a child will be able to stay in school despite the limited financial resources of the family. Social and cultural factors have to be considered, but the most important factor is the cost of the family of continued attendance at school and college.

Motherhood Challenges

The number of student mothers entering universities has been increasing around the world since 1996 and since 2001 in Iran where female compose the majority of the university students. The age of the majority female students corresponds with their reproductive age. Therefore the existence of student mothers raises concerns about the playing roles of the mothers and student. A woman may enthusiastically embrace the simultaneous roles of mother and student; however, undertaking these two roles, even in ideal conditions, can pull one person in two directions. This tradition could be harmful practice and consequently, Moreover, a Student Mothers requires the performance of heavy household and marital responsibility including the raising of the children. Different experiences and challenges of motherhood in diverse culture a role challenges cause women to abandon one role for the sake of the others.

Base on Kahn's (1979) Theory on social support the mother reported an average of seven percent support person each most typically, these were the mother's souse or partner and close friends and relative the network of social support is a major source of emotional support, aid and affirmation for the mothers during the labour the main source of emotional support for mothers was the midwife for the vast majority (85%) of the mothers childbirth was positive experience. A significant association was found between the emotional support provided by midwives and mother's positive experiences of childbirth.

Student mothers go through a number of challenges as they live double lives as mothers and students. Often challenges are faced like lack of support due to other factors like lack of finance and time being limited. A the feeling of student mothers in regards to lifestyle and the juggle multiple lifestyle as a full-time student and a full-time mom. This does make her feel disconnect from campus life. It is evident that lack of support from head of the school may influence the attitude of teacher and other learners toward the teen mother. The exclusionary approach by school is cause for concern, especially within the context of enabling national policy.

Teen mother is one of the major factors initiating school advancement of female Hallman, Grant (2004). Chevalier and Viitanen (2001), who argue that teenage mother is prove to conflict with human capital investment that typically takes place during adolescence by raising the opportunity cost of time spent in education. Early childbearing is likely to reduce labour force participation because of the low compatibility of employment and childbearing. The negative effect of early childbearing on adult wages is both direct and indirect as the wages of teenage mothers are negatively affected by reduced education and work experience. According to Chevalier and Viitanen teenage motherhood reduces the chance of post compulsory schooling by 12% to 24%. Therefore they conclude that teenage motherhood seems to impose long-term consequences on the career development of young mother and hence is likely to lead to transmitting poverty generation to generation. It would thus appear that policies preventing the long-term consequences of teenage motherhood should be focused on helping teenage mothers to succeed in their secondary school education (Chevalier & Viitanen, 2001). Several challenges confront single parent's young mothers in particular as they try to gain access to and persist in the higher education. One challenges if finding time for self while managing multiple role. Cited single parents, young mother in higher education often find themselves faced with the logical and emotional difficulty of balancing multiple roles as parent, student, employee, caregiver, and responsible head of household. The demand of these roles create additional stress on this population as they attempt to enrol in persist in college. But there are girls who are studying as well as taking care of their children and they are known to called student mothers.

The burden for the girls have double as to they have to take care of school requirements as well as their children at home. It was argued that raised of a child involves a great deal of financial, emotional, and practical planning. It is necessary to make sure that there are adequate child resources available. This may be difficult to do if the student is going to school full-time. However, if the student decides to remain in school and take care of the child it may be more possible if she has a partner of family member who will provide additional help to care for the child. Brown & Amankwaa (2007). Parenting is very stressful and some women cannot deal with all the task are involved. Although it is best to have family, friend and spousal support after giving birth to a baby. According to education for women remains the most vital tool in the promotion of equality between men and women and in the empowerment of women to contribute fully to society. The fact that they cannot finish their studies these students may have limited job opportunities in the present time the minimum requirement to get the stable job is to complete the college degree. It was predicted on the cultivation of high academic aspiration, a process of influence that begins well before high school graduation. Schooling was a critical to a young women's life

because the amount of the school a woman obtained affect the future aspect of her life.

There were advantages and disadvantages of continuing schooling while at the same time parenting a child .In addition it may be hypothesized that women returning to school demonstrate higher levels of achievement motivation..Another research voiced the concern for women if they can handle the demands of multiple roles without serious negative health consequences.Common assumptions that define adolescence as a time of storm and stress, immaturity and leisure are incongruent with cultural assumption of “good” mothering shaped around White middle class scripts, particularly those privileging economic and social authority an individualize. Critiques those who would argue that the Black community condones teen pregnancy as an acceptable form of motherhood. Many student mothers use different coping strategies to adjust to their situation. As student -mothers depend on time management to handle the many different tasks of the student-mothers. Another coping is managing tasks to handle the things needed to be done as both student and a mother as well as emotional and physical support from both the partner and parents of the student mother. Due to student mothers’ situation being difficult they have adapted coping mechanism. Mothers are more responsible than those of regular student.

He has been that girls who were irresponsible before pregnancy has been more responsible after pregnancy and is more less likely to drop-out college than the regular student. For many women, the experience of becoming a mother is a major turning point in their lives “ Often parenthood initiates an epistemological revolution”. It is as if act creation ushers in a whole new view of one’s creative capacities cited motherhood is often an expected and natural goal associated with an ethic of nurturing, care, unconditional love, idealism, and self sacrifice Josselson, (1986) Lynch (2008). Yet these idealistic attribute, while promoted society, are rarely the reality of women who are mother. Once a woman becomes a mother, she is influenced by social norms and pressures associated with that role ,but women are often unable to meet quixotic expectation. According to Lynch (2008). These non-traditional students are often student mothers and should be given special attention because aside from their role as student they also mothers and care givers at home. Many see or consider their families a hindrance to their education which is wrong they should see it as a motivator because primarily, student mother go back to studying because they want to provide for their child. A gradient of disadvantage is also apparent with young mothers in their early twenties experiencing some degree of disadvantages compared to older mothers, but not to the extended of that confronting teenage mothers . Assert that young mother including those aged in their early twenties, are one of the most impoverished groups in junior high school.

In major cases, teenage mothers are not in position to go back to school after delivery as they are forced to look after their children. In some cases these young mothers’ physical health conditions do not make it conducive for them to go back to school as the result of this factors, found that there are some cases of teenagers who may use their pregnant status to deliberately escape in demands of high school education. In this study one of the most important aspects of planning for motherhood role was the selection of an alternative method for childcare. Berge and Mamhute (2013) quotes from Mendes and state that without proper childcare and taking on the student role becomes very difficult for young mother. Managing tasks to handle the thing needed to be done as both student as well as mother’s emotional and physical support from both the partner and the parent of the student mother. In some case, financial needs make mother work while educating and this is known as financial difficulties to the mother’s academic success. The psychological pressure toward being a good mother exist not only for those mothers with dependent their little children.

Teenagers who may use their pregnant status to deliberately escape in demands of high school education.

In 2008 teen birth rates internationally per 1000 girls age 15-19, United state Kingdom had some of the highest teenage pregnancy rates in the developed world. Being a young mother in a first world country can affect one’s education. Teenage mothers are more likely to drop out of high school. However recent studies have found that many of these mothers had already drop-out of school before becoming pregnancy but those in school at the time of this pregnancy were as likely to graduate as their peers(18).One study in 2001 found that women who gave birth during their teens completed secondary level schooling 10-12 % as often and pursue post secondary education 14-29 % as often women who waited until age of 30. One of the most important responsibilities that teen mother has is being able to financially support her child. While many teen mothers may not work, they may utilize friends, family as the support of the father to pay the bills and expenses related to the child. Some teen mothers utilize welfare services to pay for raising their child. This may include financial assistance to pay rent or day care and also food stamps. If the teen mother has a good support system, she may be able to work and go to school to help support the child. Many teen mom drop-out of school when pregnant, so activities and programs that keep them in school are vital. However a high school education is not the only kind of education activities teen mom need. They benefit from child birth and parents. Although literature exist on the race and class on youth in South Africa, research in to gender and education and in particular the challenges young teen mothers go through when they go back to school, and how to address the challenges so that the girls are able to finish their schooling, remain limited. Example of the few author in this subject include who have highlighted the critical role of education and gender in Africa, who provide tools and sector-specific guidelines for gender mainstreaming. While the situation concerning teenage pregnancy and schooling problem is less accounted for locally, it widely accounted for globally Chavalier and Viitanen,2001; Helge,1989. According to the situation relating to pregnancy and schooling disturbance in South Africa are inevitably associated with social problems. These problems range from ignorance and moral collapse (Helge, 1989) to the sexual abuse of powerless female adolescent and lastly public ignorance about early menarche. According to their studies; Mothering, peer pressure and school Environment negatively affected teen mothers in coping with schooling.

Research by Kaufman et, al (2001) show that both pregnancy and parenting are the leading reasons girls give for dropping out of school. Accordingly adolescent childbearing is especially disruptive to the educational process of girls and as a consequence, many teen mothers leave school and never return. In USA, Arlington Public School (2004) further reinforce the predicament of the girls.

Teen parents face an overwhelming number of difficulties. Parental and peer pressure are far more common than support and understanding.

Mature and adult decision are required of emotional pressured adolescents. Managing to care for an infant devoting adequate time to school work is great challenges for these parenting teens (Arlington Public School 2004). In the 2000 commission on gender Equity report to the South Africa Ministry of Education, it was stated that the number of complaints had been received from pregnant learners concerning the manner in which their school had been treating them. Some form of discrimination which include suspension from the class were reported (Ministry of Education, 2000).Although it maybe illegal to refused pregnant girls an opportunity to complete their schooling. Since education is their Human Right (UNESCO, 2003). Lamented that some school committees in South Africa are often unwilling to allow girls to continue attending classes for fear that they “contaminated” other girls and encourage them to become pregnant. The unwilling is still practiced in many public school. While pregnant and teen mothering are major causes of secondary dropout for girls, social, economic, and cultural issues also make girls’ school attendance a complex decision for the girls parent. Some parent may not send girls to school because they consider the benefits of education for girls to be limited and the cost of sending them to school to be unnecessary for the family (Swainson et.al,1998,Lloyd and Mensch, 1999)The Forum for African women Educationalist(Fawe) has work since 1992 to promote education for women through advocacy concrete action and policy reforms. In the mid nineties, the forum successfully lobbied the ministries of education in several African countries to change policies that exclude pregnant girls from-entering school. According a policy formalize in 1996 allow pregnant girls and mothering teens to continue schooling logistically and financially (Grant and Hallman, 2006). Although a young single mother’s path from poverty to empowerment via education may be filled with hope, she must address critical barriers to that education due to her low-income status.

Despite the many negative outcomes associated with single parenthood, over the years the number of single mother household in America society continues to grow. The National Center for education statistic (2007) reported that 7% of full time undergraduate are single parent. This increase in single mothers on college campus remains a challenges for education. Negotiating Motherhood: the struggle of teenage mothers Approximately 10% of all birth occurs to teenage mothers worldwide.

This phenomenon is of concern because teenage mothers are reported to be disadvantaged financially, educationally, and cognitively in both the short and long term. Many teenage mothers find strength and fulfilment in their motherhood role but this those not come without cost to themselves or their children as many teenager are considered unsuitable to be parent and do not have adequate support.

Academic Activities

Academic activities intertwined challenging competitions. Therefore, motherhood responsibilities impose a large burden on students’ shoulders. The academic community focused mainly to success development un-ending competition without providing any support. Therefore, taking a motherhood along with studies is not considered normal in universities. Student Mothers experiences unpleasant emotion pressures and receive negative feedback from academic setting, implying that education is a first priority. Moreover, prejudice toward student mothers and the labelling of them as non-productive stimulate avoidance behaviours a discriminatory, allocation of educational resources for the student mothers avoid with them or hide their parenting roles. From academic perspective bring a child indicates that the student mothers does not have the required interest and enthusiasm to take the require steps for scientific development Adofo,(2013).In a study of on stress and social support among students in German Universities,the researcher found that female students experienced more stress that was negatively related to social support. In fact, social support was a social process affected health and mental wellbeing which lead to increased self-efficacy and the reduction of stress Hamdan-Mansour and Dawani , 2008), according to the finding to the study near and distant relatives, especially mothers, spouse, friends, teacher, and classmate, provide support to student mothers. In line with these finding adofo (2013) pointed to the supportive role of students spouse in financial affairs, childcare, and routine domestic task, which reduced the workload imposed on student mothers (adofo 2013).

Methodology

Research Design

In this study a qualitative descriptive design, allowing the researcher to get an in-depth understanding of experiences of Junior High School Student Mothers .Qualitative research has the advantages the uncovering the live experiences of individual by enabling them to interpret and attribute meaning to their experiences and in the process construct their worlds (Meriam and Simpson 2000, as cite in Berge & Mamhute, 2003).

By examining real-life situations, qualitative study result in a rich and holistic account of the phenomenon under investigation (Merriman, 1998).In understanding the philosophy behind qualitative methodology, researcher point out the intent to look at practical real-life instances in order to provide a total picture of the actual interaction of an event. The researcher uses a qualitative method to concentrate on specific experiences of Junior-high student mothers to identify these experiences for interview process that may be crucial but more critical in understanding the phenomenon. There is need to be a modemic understanding of the experiences, aspiration

and realization of student mothers.

Participants

The study was conducted in the schools under Maguindanao I Division namely; Datu Saudi Ampatuan National High School, Guindulungan National High School, Maguindanao National High School, Buluan National High School, Talayan National High School.

To the five schools served as a local of the study there are ten informants were a junior High student mothers are selected to answer the following inquiry.

This study used purposive sampling technique. This type of sampling start with the known sources of information who or which were in turn give other sources of information. This was focus on the lived experiences of the participants as Junior High Student Mothers.

Instrument

Informants guide questionnaire (IGQ) was used to gather information on the lived-experiences, difficulties and struggles as well as their aspiration and realization of the Junior High Student Mothers. The researcher was used the guides herself.

Procedure

After this proposal study was submitted and approach by the members. Panel, the researcher sought the approval of the letter request from the dean of the Graduate College to conduct the study. Then the letter of consent for the participants was personally distributed by the researcher.

Data Analysis

Informant guide questionnaires (IGQ) were used in the study. The researcher who is conversant in Maguindanao asked question in Maguindanao and Tagalog language the corresponding areas of local. Voice recording and transcribing were considered indispensable techniques.

To gather the data on lived experiences of Junior High Student Mothers, interviews and observations were employed. Interview was used in seeking the appropriate responses based on their true experiences.

Phenomenological Study

The research study employed phenomenological design. Phenomenology is both the description of the quality of lived experience and the description of meaning of the expressions of lived experience (Van Manen 1990 p; 25). The goal of this is to describe in detail the "every day and ordinary occurrence" of the lived experiences of junior high student mothers during the time or day to day task and interpret the theme and meaning of these experiences. In my study of the experiences of Junior-High Student Mothers the purpose of the study is to help and understand the endeavours experienced by student mothers and how the student mothers cope with their situation toward their studies and as well as child rearing.

Ethical Considerations

The sensitive nature of the study raised salient ethical issues which had to carefully considered during the research process. Consideration will take to adhere strictly to ethical measure as outlined in the faculty ethics regulations.

In order to ensure the safety and right of the participants. The researcher oriented and informed them on the nature of the study and their rights as respondent of the study. Further, the participants and parents were assured of their anonymity and confidentiality.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results and discussion of the study. The data are presented in narrative forms.

I-Experiences of Junior-High Student Mothers

All the interviews were audio-recorded with the permission of the informant and then transcribed. The informant to the questionnaires were scanned and clean manually and collected for analysis. The data was analysed by means of descriptive analytical approach.

Immediately after each session, and the interviews were transcribed verbatim and read several times to get the sense of the whole and the data was analysed using the method. Meaning units as phrase and sentence related to the experiences of motherhood were determined. The related meaning units were labelled with codes and sorted into categories and subcategories base on their similarities and differences. Lastly, similar categories were abstracted and labelled with themes and subthemes indicating there was a latent meaning in the text.

These themes and the subtheme were categorized into positive and negative experiences of the junior high student mothers.

A. Negative Experiences

a. Difficult Experiences

The difficult experiences were categorized into several themes such as difficulties on time management, financial, emotional and psychological.

Theme 1 – Difficulties on Time Management

The junior-high school mothers have experienced difficulty on time management. All the participants interviewed expressed that they do not have enough time to do their respective tasks. Most of them did multitasking when in school and when they are at home. During school days most of them experience to be late in classes because they need to do house hold chores first. The need to leave their children under the supervision of a relative. Sometimes leaving children or baby under the stewardship of somebody is quite difficult to mother's feelings. Its painful but they don't have the choice since they also need to go to school. Young mothers need to balance their time.

The following statement were taken verbatim form the different conversation of participants.

Mother 1,2,3,4,6 said “ I need to balance my time at ganito po ang ginagawa ko kapag nag-aaral ako inihiwan ko ang anak ko sa binayanan ko tapos pag uwi ko hinuhugasan ko ang mga bebron nya at naglalaba ako sa gabi tapos mag-over time ako mag study para sa mga homework ko.(Mother 1 said” I need to balance my time” then when I am go to school I left my child to my mother-in – law and then when I am back to our house I clean up the utensil such the baby bottle and after that I washed our dirty dress. When I rest a little bit I'm over time to open my lectures and to answer my homeworks.)

(Mother 3 also stated on time difficulty; Well being a student and as a mother is truly hard especially when your baby is stub born, but I need to handle it,though Icant help getting late sometimes.)

(Pag gising mo asikasuhin mo pa anak mo maglinis at pakainin mo pa anak mo bago ka umalis sa bahay kaya minsan na li late kana.Ginagawa ko na lang ay gumigising ako ng maaga para iyon time ko sa Gawain sa bahay ay maaga kung matapos at para hindi ako ma late. (When you woke up you take care of your child And you clean up, fed of it, before you will go to school and sometimes You've late. To avoid my routine task I woke up early in the morning and do what are my obligation for being a mother and a student.)

Mother 8,3,5,7 stated; ang ginagawa ko yon nga maaga akong gumigising para nang sa ganun kunti lang ang maging trabaho ni husband sa bahay. At ang isa pa ang iba kong anak pumupunta sila sa kanilang lolo at lola para mag paalaga.(Mother 8 state; I woke up early in the morning so that I do early my tasks and my husband he do a little bit in our house. Aside from that my other children they go to Our mother-inlaw and to my other sibling to take care of them.)

Time management is considered a difficulty by all respondent student mothers. Time management helps student mother in prioritizing things and accurately judge the amount of time needed to complete tasks, through their experiences , learning the different activities as a parent and as a student may requires prioritizing what is important. There are situations where one needs to attend classes and does assignments and one may need to be absent for family's sake.

As stated student mothers depends on time management to handle many different tasks of student mothers. Another support by is to adapted coping mechanism.

Theme 2 – Financial Difficulty

Most of the student-mothers mentioned that they encountered financial difficulty. Mother 1 stated “Sa pag-aaral mahirap pero masaya din mahirap kasi dalawa ang responsibilidad mo nag-aaral ka at isang ina ka pa, at sempre problema sa mga financial.” (Mother 1 said” for being a student it so hard but despite of hardship I am happy. It difficult because you have dual task or responsibilities as a student at the same time a mother. Another is on financial problem experienced.)

In line with these stated by Adofo (2013) pointed to the supportive role of students spouse in financial affairs, childcare, and routine domestic task ,which reduced the workload imposed on student mothers. Determined that being a mother had a great influence on education. The management of maternal and family affair by female student in school in which motherhood role is supported is challenge. There is a need to emphasize the significance of the role of mother and student and to provide support and education for gaining skill to play a roles. In addition, policy makers should devise strategies for bringing changes to the traditional perspective that motherhood and educational responsibilities cannot be met simultaneously by one person. The structure of schools should be family friendly. It captures the strength and strategies of the participants who also overcome challenges to academic success so that other student mother's could also achieve their goals.

Theme 3 – Emotional and Psychological Difficulties

The third theme was on emotional and psychological difficulties. The themes were categorized into two; subject for bullying and created a feeling of anxiety.

Subject for bullying. “ I was bullied in school and I was once then a subject for gossip”,(Mother 4,5,7 said. Most of us who married early were criticized by people in the community and school is not an exemption. We were able to hear bad criticisms such as “ malandi

ka”, “igat or bigan” which means flirt. keyso na ganito maaga daw ako nag-asawa at yon nga maaga akong nagkaroon ng anak at nag-aaral pa.”)

Mother 4 said” I was encountered bad criticism that I was the one who is flirting that made me married early and had a child at an early stage.

These sample criticisms affected the emotional as well psychological well being of the participants. On academic activities considered in Normal Universities student mother’s experiences unpleasant emotion pressures and receive negative feedback from academic setting, implying that education is a first priority.

Moreover, prejudice toward student mothers and labelling of them as non-productive stimulate avoidance behaviours a discriminatory, allocation of educational resources to other students. Grant and Hallman, 2006) according to a policy formalize in 1996 allow pregnant girls and mothering to continue schooling logistically and financially. Swainson et.al 1998, Lloyd Mensch, 1999 on Forum for African Women Education (FAWE) promote education for women through advocacy concrete action policy reform that change policies for exclude pregnant girls from entering school.

b. Feeling of Anxiety

Mother 1,2,3,4,5,6,8,9,10 gave their testimonies like “ Mother 1 said” Being a young mother, I felt trouble and worried especially when my child got sick. I felt disturbed for I really do not know what to do.(This happened when my child had experience “ convulsion” or sobrang taas ang lagnat, I was the only one left at home while my husband was still at the farm working.)

The feeling of anxiety is a common experience for young mothers.(Mother 3 said” Marrying at an early age, made me adjust to different situations and the adjustment to a new life having a family. When I experienced my first pregnancy, I suffered a lot of discomforts that I need to take.)

This experience affirms on the theory of social support by Kahn’s (1979) cited on the mothers reported an average of 7% support person most typically, social support is a major source of emotional support, aid and affirmation for mothers during the labour the main source of emotional support for the mothers was the midwife for the vast majority (85%) of the mothers childbirth was a positive experience.

Despite the many negative outcomes associated with a single parenthood, over the years the number of single mother household in America society continues to grow. As cited by Brown Amankwaa (2007) has found out that student mothers are more responsible than of regular student it support that the girls irresponsible before pregnancy has been more responsible after pregnancy. Motherhood is often an expected and natural goal associated with ethic of nurturing, care, unconditional love idealism, and self sacrifice.

Theme 4-Simultaneous Management

This theme consist of subtheme “ planning, and sacrificing “ Almost all the student mothers had to increase their control over situation in order to fulfil their multiple tasks as mother, student, housewife, and so on. They applied various techniques such as “ planning”. However, when duties overlapped, motherhood tasks took priority in other words they have to sacrifice.

Planning

All participant made plans to organize and prioritized their motherhood and student duties. For instances they made effort to organize home affairs, motherhood tasks, work-related duties, and financial affairs.

Mother 8 said, “ ginagawa ko ang lahat ng dapat kung gawin at kung anu ang hindi ko pa nagagawa sa buong lingo o sa isang buwan at dahil nga sa pangalawa akong asawa kailangan alam ko –kung paano ko gagawin ang mga tasking ko bilang isang ina, asawa, at studyante.(I do all my tasks as early as I can do even in weekend or in a month for doing and finished as early. Because I am a second wife I need to manage and planned what and how to do my dual role as a student and a mother.)

The most important things in the planning of motherhood duties emphasized by the participants was seeking an appropriate reminders. Mother 2 said, When my husband do not take care of our children because he had work that needs to be rash and finished in the farm. I have to leave my children with my mother-in-law who live as our neighbourhood for a whole day. Financial affairs also needed some sort of planning and organizing so that educational cost and for other expenses could be provided and paid.

Mother 9 said, para po sa akin kung anu ang talagang pinaka kailangan ng aming pamilya yon lang ang binibili ko.at tuwing pasukan ang ginagawa ko po binabayaran ko na ang mga miscellaneous namin sa buong taon para dina kasali sa listahan ko at pagba budget ko.dahil nga sa nag aaral ang panganay ko kailangan ko talaga ib budget ang aming pera. Minsan nga nagging kuripot ako sa mga anak ko lalo na pag may project kami hindi maiwasan na makagastos.

(For me what is the most important needed by our family the only thing that I will bought. During enrolment or schooling time I had pay the miscellaneous intended for a year so that I could set aside from my expenses and for not included in our daily life budget. My eldest child also a studying. I need to budget our money sometimes I’m become selfish and thrifty to my children especially I have a project need to fix it).

Sacrificing

Participants planned, had multiple responsibilities, and faced unpredictable situation. Therefore, they had to prioritize their duties and mainly “ preferred their family and children over their studies. These are supported by the responses of the participants saying: Mother 4 said,” kapag may sakit ang anak ko lalo na pag sobrang lagnat na (convulsion) na nagkataon na may examination na kami, yon nga hindi na ako naka punta sa school at dina ako naka exam dahil gusto kung ang anak ko ang maisalba ko at isakripisyo ko ang pag-aaral ko kaysa anak ko. Dahil hindi rin ako maka concentrate kung iniwan mo anak mo na may sakit. Maisip mo pa na pag may masamang mangyari sa anak mo habang buhay mo ito na pagsisisihan.

Mother 4 said; when my child get sick and experience convulsion at the same time I had an examination. So I decide to stay at home and took care of my child Its better to give up my study than to leave my child were sick, because I don't focus in my examination. When we encountered a problem in our home especially about your children are involved. I think as a mother I need to sacrifice one of my role for what will happen of my child I might regret for the rest of my life.

On this situation managing tasks to handle the things needed to be done as both student and a mother as well as emotional and physical support from both the partner and the parent of the student mother. Expressed one could adapted coping mechanism such as problemfocused, avoidance and emotion-focused strategies and one may received upon resuming studies the spiritual and social support.

B. Positive Experiences

Theme 5- Harmonious Experiences

This theme was categorized also into two subtheme satisfaction/fulfilment, and positive experiences.

a. Satisfaction/Fulfilment

Mother 1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10 or all of them expressed their happiness by saying “mother 1;ang kasiyahan ko ang anak ko na kapag nakikita ko siyang tumatawa walag kapantay ang saya ko. (my happiness when I glance and saw my child/children that laughing and smiling myhappiness is beyond compared and my exhaustion can't get the best of me). This proves one of their source of happiness are the children. Seeing children with their smile means happiness and feeling of satisfaction/fulfilment. It seems that children were source of energy amidst of the difficulties and hardships.

b. Positive Experiences

Mother 5 also stated that she experienced positive treatment from school. Both teacher and their classmate treated her equally that created a positive atmosphere and brought harmonious relationship among people.

Theme 6- Comprehensive Support

All participants strongly believed the receiving support for emotional, financial, mothering, housekeeping, and educational aspects of life facilitated taking roles and responsibilities.

Mother 2 said, My parents as well as my mother-in-law were played the main role in our educational success since my husband is also a student I am schooling today we are both students. She cited, (ang biyanan ko din ang sumusuporta sa amin sa gastusin, at pag aalaga sa anak l laming ay siya lahat).

Support may come from the student's husband, family members, schools, teachers, classmates. Based on the support source, these factors are categorize into situational and institutional support.

Mother 4,6,10 and, “mother 10 stated”(ang asawa ko ay talagang matulongin at lagi niya akong ini encouraged, ang sabi nya hanggat l l n gami pa at kaya mo pang mag-aral mag-aral ka. Sa mga Gawain sa bahay minsan siya na ang gumagawa, lalo na pag time ng examination ko, hindi na niya ako gina isturbo).

(Mother 10 stated” my husband have given full support. He help me in doing the household chores, he always encouraged me to study until I can do.especially during my examination.)

Mother 5 said, Nag papasalamat ako sa aming school dahil may program sila na open-high school na kung saan sinusupurtahan nila ang mga kagaya ko na student mothers, at naiintindihan nila aming kalagayan.

(Mother 5 said; I thankful to our school because they provide a program such as open-high-school. In here, all the student mothers are given chances to continue our dream to finish schooling and we were motivated because they understand our situation.)

Institutional facilities (Open- High School Program), this is a program that support the junior High School student mothers to pursue their schooling in order to finish her studies. Cited Ministry of Education , 2000 and the Human Right By UNESCO, 2003; Although it may be illegal to refused a pregnant girls an opportunity to complete their schooling since education is their Human Right.

Another implication they stated the most important factor is the cost of family to continue attendance at school and college despite

the limited financial resources of the family.

II. Aspirations and Realizations

For a young junior-high school student mothers, there were a lot of testimonies being shared regarding their aspirations. They mentioned of aspiring to finish school so they can help and support the needs of the family. Parenting is very stressful and some women cannot deal with all the task are involved although it is best to have family, friend, spousal support after giving a birth to a baby. Another aspirations is to find a job after schooling to earn a living for they realized that to be married requires financial stability. Most of them realized the difficulty of doing dual roles, as a student and as a mother or wife. These roles somehow contributed to the difficulties encountered. They realized the value of time. The need to use time wisely.

Realization

For them being a young mother, they were able to realize that motherhood requires so many things. There are do's and don'ts being a married woman. They were stress to do many obligations as a student and as a mother and wife. Teen parent face an overwhelming number of difficulties. Parental and peer pressure are far more common than support and understanding. Mature and adult decisions are required of emotional pressured adolescent. Managing to care for an infant devoting adequate time to school work is great challenges for those parenting teens.

Time Management is seen as the common experiences for these student mothers. Because the live dual roles as a mother and as a student, they struggle to split their time to accommodate all their responsibilities. This supported work, student mothers greatly depend on time management. For coping the respondents commonly rely on being positive and not being stressed about their situation. as for the factors they consider that great helped them cope the common factor was the help support of the family members and husband. This is supported works that lessen the dual tasks on the student mothers if there are people around her who can support and help in caring for the child.

This is evident as stated by (Mother 2,5,6) when she has to go to school specially in time of examination, and when she has things to needs to do at home her mother-in-law as well as her husband is the one who take care of the child. Mother 6,8 stated that her mother-in-law support her both financially and caring for the child at home.

In this study positive experiences of motherhood were associated with good social support which contributed to feeling of acceptance and optimistic for student mother and also brought them closer to their families (particular mother and female siblings) and they valued having a child whom they loved and who loved them back, and student mother can strengthen relationship and seal the woman's place in a relationship, marriage and within the community.

Conclusions

Based on the results of this study, the following recommendations could be adopted and put into practice as to help student mothers to copes their difficulties and to succeed in their education and also found in this study and administered to other economically and eligible and community junior high student mothers. Focus on availability of support system, preparation for college, and motivational factors for persistence, and balance between multiple roles.

Community college provides a path to a two-year degree which limit the possibilities for income and career paths. A meta analysis of programs and services offered at public institution for students who are mother would provide a solid foundation for further analysis and recommendation on how to best serve these student. Those program and services that were the most effective at retaining students could be replicate as best practices on a national scale.

Provision of proper counselling to the student mothers before they return to the school system; Teachers may design lesson plan , and provide time available for teen mothers at time that are convenient to them were proper counselling could be done. Provide teacher training on how to support student mothers in their schools; Schools may consider Santiago 49 providing facilities and other alternative measures were could enhance their skills as young mothers.

Recommendations for further studies

A study on the Effects of early Marriage to student performances.

Experiences of Teacher handling Student Mothers.

Challenges for coping strategies in handling dual role.

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